

MUSICAL ENVIRONMENT AND MUSICAL THOUGHT SPECIFIC TO EASTERN AND EUROPEAN PEOPLE

Olimova F.B.

Doctoral student at the Institute for the Study of Youth Problems and Training of Prospective
Personnel under the Youth Affairs Agency

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14195805>

Abstract. *This article is dedicated to the distinctiveness of musical thought in Eastern and European countries, as well as the commonalities and differences in the musical environments that have facilitated the resolution of ethnopyschological scientific hypotheses related to musical thought characteristic of these regions.*

Keywords: *emotion, tone, educational opportunities, musical environment, traditional forms, improvisational music, religious music, music theory forms, formal structures, composition, development.*

Introduction. Regardless of a person's nationality, religion, or origin, there has always been a need for music in their life activities, providing them with spiritual nourishment. Musical thought and environment significantly differ between Eastern and European countries. These differences are based on historical, cultural, philosophical, and practical factors. This undoubtedly embodies musical thought and the national musical values specific to each people, highlighting the invaluable importance of music as an art form in the formation of human identity, its divinity, and its connection to spirituality—a point that contemporary researchers and past scholars have consistently emphasized. In particular, the genius of Uzbek poetry, Alisher Navoi, expresses remarkable thoughts on this subject in one of his prose works: “The singer who enhances joy and the musician who dispels sorrow are both cherished by sensitive individuals and those who share in their pain. When they perform with gentle melodies, it is no wonder if the listeners' very lives are devoted to the music. After all, the soul draws strength from pleasant melodies, while the spirit feeds on beautiful sounds.”

Main Part. Music serves to shape the spiritual, artistic, and moral culture of the younger generation, enrich their thought and perception, foster national pride, patriotism, elegance, and creativity, broaden their worldview, and promote independence and initiative.

The vast educational potential of music emerges only through the serious professional preparation of the teacher and their continuous attention to developing the musical creative abilities of the student. Moreover, one of the critical factors determining the effectiveness of music education is the theoretical development of musical methodological issues and their relevance to practice. Regarding the musical environment, the theoretical-methodological and scientific-methodical significance of music education in both Eastern and Western regions defines its unique characteristics, objectives and tasks, laws, theoretical foundations, and methodological directions within the context of musical environments.

It is well-known that musical thought is a form that reflects complex and multifaceted relationships among musical sounds based on objects of cognition—things, events, and occurrences—within human consciousness. For a long time, the complexities of musical thought have kept it outside the purview of psychologists [1. – p. 26].

Musical thought arises from musical feeling and perception and relies on vocal, musical, and artistic images in the performance of a musical work. It is a specific intellectual process of understanding the uniqueness and laws of musical culture as well as comprehending a work of musical art. The specificity of musical thought is linked to the development of musical abilities as well as to the musical environment and conditions in which a person lives and is educated.

Analyzing the differences in musical environments between Eastern and Western countries is appropriate, particularly concerning musical culture, musical thought, perception, and musical imagery. In analyzing the music culture and heritage of Eastern peoples alongside pedagogical aspects within the bachelor's program in music education, various classifications exist regarding students' musical thought environments, these include:

- according to the analysis of scientific literature, the heritage of traditional music consists of improvisational, instrumental, religious and musical theoretical forms;
- as for the "Traditional" forms of music, such concepts as makom, bench and makom occupy an important place in the traditions of Eastern music, therefore it is called religious;
- each status has its own musical structure and timbres and, accordingly, shows the features of the organization of musical thinking;
- an improvisation process in Eastern music. Improvisation is an important process that is similar to making unique discoveries in the performance of music, and is of great importance in performance. Here, musical performers will be able to demonstrate their creative discoveries;
- if we talk about religious musical forms and the influences that are carried out through them, then in this case, music is often associated with religious ceremonies and holidays, and it is because of these religious views that it is found in existing ceremonies. Islam, Buddhism and other religions, religious views of the population had a great influence on Eastern music.

In Eastern music, the issues of "Instrumentation and instrumental work" have acquired great importance. In particular, such forms existing in Eastern music are reflected in the works of many art historians, musicologists, ethnomusicologists, teachers, ethnopedagogues and music teachers, and this situation is subjectively based on the origin of instrumental words and it can be noted that this is characterized in connection with the peculiarities of application in the glue process. In particular, at first, such special instruments as rubob, tanbur, flute and oud were widespread in Eastern music. Later, the sounds of these instruments acquire increasing importance in the development of musical forms due to their performance characteristics.

The "musical-theoretical" view also shows that in Eastern music there are also stable phenomena, musical forms, the existence of correspondences based on the theory and methodology of music in the environment of musical thought. This, in turn, gives the opportunity to performers and listeners to develop a culture of creating, performing and listening to complex melodies.

Eastern music is predominantly monodic. That is why he included thinking based on monody. Eastern music is characterized by horizontal development of musical thinking using numerous scale forms (more than 80), quarter-tones, semitones, glissando techniques, rich rhythmic structure, non-temporal relationship of sounds, diversity of timbres and melody. Musical thinking and the musical environment in the countries of the East have many features. As a result, traditional musical forms, masters who created many works, and various cultures are formed among them.

In Western music, unique pedagogical and psychological thinking has been created. According to the characteristics of the environment of musical thought in the field of music, its most important aspects and basic methods, forms and styles are distinguished: tonality, formal structures, composition, development and aesthetic musical-philosophical forms. on the tonal system, which allows musical works to have clear tonal centers and harmonic development.

In the same way, formal structures play an important role in the classical forms of Western music (symphony, sonata, quartet). These formal structures systematically organize musical compositions.

Definitely, musical composition plays an important role in writing a piece of music, whether it is Eastern or Western music.

Composition. The melodic features of Western music are often focused on composition and structure. Composers develop musical ideas using various formal and harmonic methods. The development of music includes various musical periods in the history of Western music, such as the Baroque, Classical, Romantic and Modern styles.

Such advanced musical works deeply reflect the psychological, pedagogical, aesthetic and philosophical aspects of music. Music expresses human feelings and thoughts through performance and composition. For Western musical culture, homophonic-harmonic thinking is characteristic of the vertical development of musical thinking associated with the logic of the movement of the harmonic sequence. Musical thinking has been studied since ancient times. It can be said that the system of relationships of musical sounds discovered by Pythagoras during his experiments on the monochord style laid the foundation for the development of musical thinking [2. - B.20-21].

Above we have considered the features of the categories of musical thinking, different sides of the characteristics of both regions, and now we will analyze the common components of the musical environment. "Cultural interaction", the musical culture of the Eastern countries has problems of interaction. For example, Arabic, Turkish and Persian music are largely influenced by each other.

In music education, the traditional system of music education among Eastern peoples is often built on the principle of "teacher-student". This allows preserving unique styles and forms of music. Such a system is the system of makomat, this is the system of makomat in Arabic music, which are melodic and harmonic structures. Each status can represent a certain emotional state and time.

Indian classical music includes the performance of ragas, which is a system of ragas in Indian music, representing different times and states of mind. The structure and performance of ragas are based on certain rules and styles. One of the unique features of Eastern and Western music is the widespread use of various styles of improvisation in creativity. That is, free performance is of great importance. Music performers contribute to the performance process based on musical traditions. This shows the technical skill and creativity of the performer. Musical system In Eastern music, time signatures (method) and melodic systems are of great importance. For example, Turkish music has "usul" (rhythmic structures) and a melodic system.

One of the common features of the musical environment is the development of musical instrument performance traditions. Eastern music has many traditional instruments such as sitar, tabla, oud, kanun and flute. Each instrument has its own sound quality and performance style. Many musical instruments, such as sitar and tabla, are used to create different melodic and

rhythmic structures. Music is often performed at folk festivals or religious ceremonies. Thus, musical instruments in Western music include keyboard instruments (piano, organ), symphony orchestra instruments (violin, cello) and modern music technology. Each musical instrument has its own sound and performance style.

Western music education is often carried out in formal educational institutions, conservatories and universities. This educational system includes academic, technical and creative approaches. Music performed at musical events, concerts and festivals is performed for academic and commercial purposes.

Methods of teaching and education of music, interaction of participants in the educational process through musical activities should lead to the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities of undergraduate students of music education, the development of musical and aesthetic qualities. The methodology of teaching and education of music reflects the general creative nature of the educational process [6. - B.58].

Many orientalists, in particular Abu Nasr Farabi, in his multi-volume work "The Great Book of Music" provided information on the theory and history of music, various musical instruments, melodies and their internal structure, sounds, rhythms, tones. He founded the science of cognition and science. In the mentioned work, he notes that musicologists and researchers of the past have made a great contribution to the development of music. He also talks about the harmony of melodies and the ways of performing a melody. According to the stories, Farabi created a new musical instrument, composed a melody and established himself as an experienced musician. Farabi says that musical ideas come from the most sensitive part of the human soul and affect feelings in the form of a melody.

In accordance with the general cultural development, it is necessary to recognize that this front was formed and effectively developed in a very short period of the history of our country. The uniqueness of the musical heritage in the musical culture of the peoples of the West and the East is that the many-thousand-year experience of the population is useful not only to use, but also to master the laws of creativity, to use it as a student in using. The rich possibilities of Uzbek folk music have the possibility of application in the education of youth. A completely new musical process has begun in Uzbek folk music, based on the creation of pop works in modern musical performance, the music of developed countries of the world. This does not exclude musical instruments. In particular, along with foreign musical instruments, percussion and wind instruments, electronic musical instruments began to be widely used. Along with the art of composition, the art of composition was widely developed [3. – B.7-8].

The distinctive features of musical thought in Eastern and Western cultures, as well as the knowledge dedicated to the musical environment, are based on scientific analyses and several structural components. These elements are grounded in educational and pedagogical systems and plans that have been thoughtfully developed for music, similar to other fields, forming a continuous process. This means that in each session, specific goals are systematically achieved step by step. Therefore, based on the aspects of the musical environment, the education sector must harmoniously conduct the physical and conscious upbringing of the younger generation as individuals. The educational significance of the musical environment and thought in both regions lies in the observation that young people can align themselves with the essence of music.

In conclusion, it should be noted that while this article has provided a detailed analysis of the characteristics of musical thought and environment in both regions, there are still many

principles and tools related to the importance of musical thought that require scientific analysis. The musical thought and environment of Eastern and Western peoples are filled with unique and rich traditions. They play a crucial role in enriching humanity's cultural heritage. To further explore this topic, it is essential to read, study, and analyze numerous literatures, draw scientific pedagogical-psychological conclusions, and develop recommendations that can ensure the advancement of the respective fields. The differences in musical thought and environment between the East and West reflect the diversity of music and the intercultural interactions on a global scale. Eastern music tends to express more improvisation and spiritual objectives, while Western music focuses on tonal and structural approaches. These differences are reflected in musical performance, composition, and education, naturally contributing to enriching the musical heritage of both regions and elevating the field of education.

REFERENCES

1. Yuldoshev U.Yu. Development of creative thinking of future music teachers based on works of national importance. Diss. Tashkent-2021. Page 26.
2. Kadirov R.G. Psychology of music, Music Publishing House. Tashkent- 2005. Pp. 20-21.
3. Pandzhiev K.B., Salimova D. Vocals and modern music. "Innovation-Intellect". Tashkent-2019.
4. Zufarova M.E. Interesting psychology. Philosophers. Tashkent-2017.
5. Yuldoshev U.Yu. (2021). Pedagogical and psychological approaches to the professional training of future music teachers. Current scientific journal of pedagogy, 2(10), 56-61.
6. <https://arxiv.uz/documents>
7. <https://lib.bimm.uz>